
LISTENING COMPREHENSION DIFFICULTIES IN SLA

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Abstract: Listening is essential in the academic process and everyday communication, this is the language skill that is used regularly. Many researchers gave the definition to the term “listening”. According to Chastain (1977), listening is the capability to comprehend authentic speech at a natural pace. To understand the message the learners hear the speech, isolate sounds, arrange them into syntactic and lexical groups.

Key words: cognitive strategies, comprehensive strategies, accents, speed of listening, parsing, perceptual processing, phonology, accumulating input.

Development of listening ability was ignored in second language acquisition, Osada (2004) noted that listening skill did not attain appropriate acceptance, but was regarded as a less active skill, that will evolve independently, until the introduction of Communicative Language Teaching. Students were taught real-world communication, and in its turn, listening was an essential skill.

Hamouda (2013), stated that due to the education system at schools and universities, where the vocabulary, grammar, and reading were more centralized, learners have substantial problems with listening comprehension. That is to say that educators neglect speaking and listening skills during the lessons, as these skills were not covered in many textbooks. Therefore, listening and speaking have become unimportant for both instructors and students. As a result, a great number of learners come across difficulties in listening. In order to help students, develop listening comprehension, instructors should analyze their listening problems in comprehending oral texts and instruct them sufficient listening comprehension strategies, in order to assist them to overcome listening comprehension difficulties.

In this current paper, We will clarify learners’ difficulties when listening to oral passages as well as strategies of listening perception. This review paper tended to enhance educators’ awareness of these problems in listening comprehension so that productive actions could be taken.

What is listening comprehension?

Various researchers defined the term “listening comprehension”. Brown and Yule (1983), defined it as the ability of an individual to comprehend whatever they hear. People will understand the passage if they listen to it. According to Rost (2002)

when learners are engaged in making sense in interactive activity this is listening comprehension. Listeners comprehend the speech input with the help of background knowledge, emphasis, and tone of voice, grammar constructions, etc.

Anderson (1983; 1985) defined three processes connected to listening comprehension, namely utilization, parsing, and perceptual processing. The audio information is concealed as mindful processes concentrated on the oral passage in perceptual processing. Attention span is narrow incapacity, this is the range of compound messages that can be comprehended at one moment. People normally struggle in completing several difficult tasks at a time, particularly if all need complete concentration. When it comes to parsing, messages and words can be interpreted into a reasonable mental image. The peace of information processed will depend on the student’s level of awareness of the language. Lastly, utilization, which consists of connecting the mental image of the passage meaning to present knowledge. It can be challenging to absorb the data, if the person has no connection for the new data, due to the absence of existing memory associations with which it can be linked.

Listening Comprehension Strategies.

Instructors should teach their learners effective listening strategies, previously enhancing the students’ background knowledge about phonology, grammar, and vocabulary

Various researchers have developed an interest in listening comprehension theory (O’Malley, Chamot, & Walker, 1987; Oxford & Crookall, 1989; Wenden & Robin, 1987). Oxford (1990) explains that as a technique to develop the usage of target language data students use language learning strategies. Andrea Helena Priolette (2005), claims that listening comprehension develops grammar and vocabulary skills, as they are important instruments in evolving literacy. Reading out loud is a simple strategy utilized in a range of schools to improve listening understanding. Listening to Audiobooks is the best choice to attract students into reading, so creating great inspiration for learning. According to O’Malley and Chamot (1989) can be divided into cognitive, metacognitive, and socio-affective groups. The last category, nevertheless, was an additional one to illustrate the interactive learning process of groupmates, require the instructor for the explanation, or utilize a special approach to minimize anxiety. These three strategies can alter depending on the level of the student

Cognitive strategies

Cognitive strategies are connected to comprehending and accumulating input in memory, short-term and long-term, for further usage. Understanding starts with gained information that is checked as successive design and a process of concealing. Azmi Bingol et al. (2004) defined that the problem-solving method that students use

in doing listening exercises is cognitive strategy. Goh (1998) stated that students use cognitive strategies to help them to contain, process, and retain new data. According to O'Malley and Chamot (1990), cognitive techniques are used when the students interact with the information either mentally or physically. Cognitive techniques can be divided into two types: bottom-up and top-down. Bottom-up techniques are most appropriate for beginners, when they translate every word, arrange the speech rate, repeat the oral passage. Furthermore, they include the concept of the stress of the syllable, intonation, phrases, and sounds. Proficient learners mostly utilize the bottom-up approach, as it includes predicting, inferring, imagining, and clarifying. According to the experiment, with university students learning Spanish, conducted by Abdalhamid (2012) cognitive strategies were used more rather than metacognitive ones, and metacognitive strategies were used more by female students than male learners. The results of the findings show that listening success was linked to skills, strategies, and efficient application of background knowledge.

Metacognitive strategies

Wenden (1985) stated that metacognitive strategies are essential in listening comprehension, as they connect learning control and learning knowledge through planning, checking, changing monitoring, and evaluating. Wenden (1998) defines that through metacognitive approach learning can become faster they become permanent acceptors and solve all problems, they feel confidence to ask for assistance from instructors, peers, family members, and are able to examine and evaluate themselves. According to Salataci (2002) capability to accomplish the task, inspiration, self-assurance in listening process can be raised by metacognitive strategies. There are also two types of metacognitive ability, which are regulation of cognition and knowledge of cognition. The former is related to student's awareness of what is happening around, the latter is related to the actions of the learner to listen productively. Metacognitive strategies can identify the diversity of the listeners skills, where capable listeners try to concentrate age after failing of understanding, while less skilled listeners pursue listening.

Socio-affective strategies

These are strategies that deal with efficient regulation over learning and cooperation in communication. A clear example of this can be peer interaction to gain educational aim, requesting the teacher for an explanation, or being optimistic in task achievement.

Listening Comprehension Difficulties

Azmi Bingol et al (2014) claim that there is a wide range of challenges in comprehension in listening, which should be identified and eliminated, to help learners to overcome the difficulties such as:

-accent (speech with an accent can lead to decrease understanding)

-speed of listening (listeners only follow the listening passage, and cannot control the pace of the track, therefore some difficulties occur in listening sessions)

-length of the material (short listening activities are more effective among learners with a low level of knowledge)

-cultural differences (instructors should provide the learners with basic knowledge of the target language to avoid problems in understanding)

-quality of recorded materials (low quality of recorded material can negatively influence listeners comprehension)

Conclusion

In many English language classrooms, listening comprehension has been neglected and undermined. Due to fact that listening comprehension is not an easy process, the strategies should be utilized synchronically. While listening multiple processes happen in the mind, like listening and comprehending the passage, using shot and long-term memory to retrieve the data, correlate all the acquired information with the background knowledge to the following one. Teachers can assist the learners by applying appropriate strategies during the classes. Although there is no universal kind of English listening lesson, listening materials must match the level of the listener, in this way some difficulties can be escaped.

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